

DYNAMIC RELATIONSHIP OF SHOPPING BEHAVIOR WITH SHOPPING EXPERIENCE, MOTIVATION ORIENTATION, AND SHOPPING FREQUENCY AT SHOPPING MALLS OF QUETTA CITY, PAKISTAN.

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DOI:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17541205>

Keywords

Customer Shopping Behavior, Shopping Experience, Shopping Frequency, Shopping Motivation Orientation, Shopping Malls, Quetta, Pakistan.

Article History

Received: 15 September 2025

Accepted: 25 October 2025

Published: 06 November 2025

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Abstract

The study examines the impact of shopping experience, shopping behavior, and shopping frequency on customer shopping behavior in Quetta City's shopping malls. Four hundred twenty patrons of shopping malls in Quetta, Pakistan, were selected by convenience sampling to participate in a self-administered survey. The study applied a multiple regression approach to test the data empirically using SPSS.

The study concluded that there is a strong correlation among the variables and that customer shopping experience, customer shopping behavior, and customer shopping frequency have a significant impact on customer shopping behavior in Quetta City's shopping malls.

INTRODUCTION

Since easy and enjoyable shopping visits might lead to increased spending and unusual perspectives on shopping behavior, mall experiences have been the focus of recent scholarly studies (Alnawas & Aburub, 2016; Barari et al., 2020; Mustikasari et al., 2021). Enhancements to customer behavior and shopping experiences have been covered in the literature (Im et al., 2010). Despite the disparities in conceptualizing mall experiences, research indicates that mall patrons assess their shopping experience based on their subjective reactions to customers' purchasing behavior (Jüttner et al., 2013), which are

known as cognitive and affective reactions (Lemon & Verhoef, 2016).

There has been a significant increase in the number of shopping malls constructed in Pakistan over the past twenty years. As a result, there is now a greater concentration of retail options and greater business potential, particularly with the rise of popular items. In addition, Rosenbaum et al. (2016) state that the atmosphere in shopping centers is advantageous for attracting people and conveying the mall's overall design. Additionally, this evolution has led to a shift in corporate operations away from traditional dual-

channel models, resulting in changes in customer preferences and an evident decline in the motivation and frequency of trips to shopping malls (Diallo et al., 2018). This transition has also led to a change in how customers interact with businesses. Generally speaking, well-developed retail malls can be found throughout Pakistan's major urban centers. According to Kinley et al. (2010), a sizeable proportion of individuals in the United States of America perceive shopping as a social activity they enjoy. One of the most important factors influencing a customer's comfort in making a purchase is their impression of a particular product category. According to O'Cass (2004), there is a relatively extensive degree of familiarity with the fashion and garment industry. The other side of the coin is that this raises the question of why different customers have varied perceptions about the same retail environment. While some individuals may find it overwhelming and unpleasant, others might find it engaging and appealing. One of the most significant factors contributing to this variety is how customers approach their purchase experiences. According to Côté-Hamel (2012) and Michon (2005), individuals hold diverse viewpoints regarding the benefits of environments similar to malls. While some believe they are beneficial, others view them as indulgent choices. According to El-Adly and Eid (2016), mall owners have recently realized that effective customer experience management is essential to the success of their businesses. According to Djelassi et al. (2018), the overall design of the shopping mall, including the arrangement of businesses and displays, has a substantial effect on the shopping experience and ultimately influences customer behavior. It is because the shopping mall's design involves arranging businesses and displays. A study by Merrilees & Miller (2019) found that the structural components of a shopping mall significantly influence customers' experiences while in the mall. Extraordinary experiences are becoming increasingly important to customers, who are seeking them more frequently.

The objective of this research is to analyze various aspects of shopping malls, with particular emphasis on developing nations such as Pakistan, where the concept is somewhat familiar. There has been limited research on the demographic characteristics

of Baluchistan, one of the country's largest provinces. This research has focused on the relationship between the characteristics of the province's population and enterprise performance. With this in mind, the purpose of the study is to investigate marketing strategies in Quetta City. It aims to identify how the shopping mall's ambiance and characteristics influence customers' shopping motives and the frequency of their visits.

The findings of this study will shed light on available options, entertainment choices, advertising strategies, factors contributing to convenience, and the site's accessibility. Furthermore, as a consequence of this, the comprehension of these components will be enhanced through the conduct of a significant study, and the gaps that are now present in the existing body of literature will be filled. It is essential to acknowledge the significant contributions that this thesis offers to the field of marketing scholarship. The construction of shopping malls aims to create a focal point for social interaction, which has been identified as one of the most significant challenges observed. Clients who prefer making purchases rather than exploring at their leisure may be dissuaded from patronizing this type of architecture. Additionally, it is feasible to gain insights into customers' browsing behaviors and motivations by studying them across a range of settings, including transit hubs and online platforms. Additionally, the research reveals, both theoretically and practically, that specific individuals feel at ease in mall social situations, which eventually leads to encounters aimed at enhancing collaboration. This is the case since malls are created to be places where people can engage with one another. Additionally, merchants can gain a more in-depth understanding of individual purchase motivations and consumer types, allowing them to adjust their sales strategies by distinguishing between social shopping and task-oriented shopping habits among their customers.

Research Questions

Is there a significant impact of customers' shopping experience on shopping behavior in shopping malls?

Does customer shopping motivational orientation significantly impact shopping behavior in shopping malls?

Is there a significant impact of shopping frequency on shopping behavior among customers in shopping malls?

Significance of the Study

In various ways, this research is beneficial to key stakeholders. In the first place, it improves our understanding of customer psychology regarding shopping behaviors in shopping malls, as well as the influence these behaviors have on motivation levels and purchase frequency. Secondly, it provides marketers with valuable insights into client behavior, equipping them to refine their responses and achieve more favorable outcomes for mall retail firms. In addition, this study helps small businesses better understand their customers' responsiveness, facilitating the implementation of improved business processes and achieving enhanced performance outcomes. In addition, it assists regulatory agencies in understanding the consequences of standard operating procedures (SOPs) at the mall level, enabling them to identify deficiencies and develop more effective procedures. In conclusion, this research offers academics a deeper understanding of the subject's significance, which, in turn, encourages more in-depth inquiries from various perspectives.

There has been an increase in the number of shopping malls in Pakistan, which customers have welcomed positively. The findings of this study (Lucia-Palacios et al., 2020a) underline the significance of customer experiences and the knowledge of themed events. Malls have successfully integrated both local and international brands, thereby improving the customer experience (El-Adly, 2019). Also, these retail malls have created a lively atmosphere, contributing to the attractive layouts they offer customers. According to Kwon et al. (2016), these establishments offer guests a variety of entertainment options, including amusement areas, movies, and children's play zones, to provide a comprehensive experience. In addition, shopping malls across the country offer shoppers a positive experience by providing convenient shopping, ample parking, and a variety of dining options (Elmashhara & Soares, 2019).

Literature Review

Customer's Shopping Behavior

According to Kwon et al. (2016), mall managers have acknowledged the value of marketing tactics and support in influencing customer purchase behavior. According to Lucia-Palacios et al. (2016), positive

shopping experiences have been linked to increased motivation to adopt better buying practices and to influence customer behavior. According to El-Adly and Eid (2016), mall managers have acknowledged the benefits of personalized organizational tools in establishing creative management strategies to enhance consumer experiences and address problems that arise during shopping. According to Lucia-Palacios et al.'s 2020a research, these tactics ultimately contribute to changes in user behavior and foster a sense of vibrancy in shopping malls. In addition, this strategy has been recognized as a departure from obsessive purchasing behaviors, highlighting its impact on human reactivity (Elmashhara & Soares, 2019). According to Rabbane et al. (2012) and Rosenbaum et al. (2016), shopping malls offer a diverse range of commercial establishments that cater to various customer preferences, thereby intensifying competition among businesses operating within these spaces. Additionally, it has been demonstrated that this diversity affects the choices available to customers during their decision-making processes while shopping (Blázquez, 2014).

Furthermore, it has been discovered that factors regulating impulsive responses can influence customer practices without detracting from the appeal intended to attract customers' attention (Altinay et al., 2019). According to research by Diallo et al. (2018) and Leonard et al. (2004), customers who lack clearly defined preferences and routines are more likely to engage in more active purchasing behaviors than those with greater awareness of their interests. In a similar vein, those who exhibit illogical behaviors are more susceptible to external stimuli, which can result in mood swings and spur unplanned purchases, in contrast to people with more rational mindsets (Atulkar & Kesari, 2017). In consumer behavior, the tendency to avoid excess is often evident in purchasing decisions. Fugate (2007), Hazen et al. (2017), and McDonald and Rundle-Thiele (2017) all agree that behaviors are shaped by encouraging human actions that produce observable effects.

Customer's Shopping Experiences

The act of shopping is often seen as a way to elevate one's mood. On the other hand, it has been shown

to contribute to impulsive purchasing behaviors, particularly when individuals are confronted with limited financial resources and heightened emotional responses (Niemelä et al., 2019). According to Niemelä et al. (2017), consumers' decision-making process has been influenced by the growth of retailers offering a wide range of brands and products. According to Atulkar and Kesari (2017), consumers who face a vast product assortment frequently experience uncertainty. It is especially true for consumers with varying levels of experience in the shopping industry. According to Lee Taylor and Cosenza (2002), customers with less experience shopping in department stores or malls tend to make poor decisions, negatively affecting their overall shopping experience. According to Diallo et al. (2018), mall management and personnel often work hard to cultivate a pleasant shopping atmosphere, enabling new consumers to make decisions more easily and ensuring they have a nice first experience. The findings of Altinay et al. (2019) and Paulins and Geistfeld (2003) indicate that shopping assistance can enhance favorable purchasing experiences, particularly for customers who are inexperienced in malls. In turn, positively affects customers' inclination to return.

Additionally, it has been demonstrated that the availability of assistance can improve customers' overall shopping experience in malls and foster positive perceptions of the experience (Knox & Denison, 2000). According to Lucia-Palacios et al.'s 2020a research, a great shopping experience typically has a positive impact on the overall definition of customer experiences. Several studies have examined the various levels of shopping inputs, aiming to shed light on customer brand affiliations and their significance in shaping customer experiences (Kwon et al., 2016). According to Lucia-Palacios et al. (2018), customers frequently experience emotional reactions during shopping, which play a key role in determining their overall level of pleasure. Pantano and Naccarato (2010) found that those who encountered entertainment elements while shopping tended to report having more pleasant experiences throughout their shopping trips. It has also been found to explain unexpected experiences (Babin et al., 1994; Zamzuri et al., 2018). Furthermore, the physical environment of shopping malls is closely

associated with determining customer-level experiences.

Customer's Motivational Shopping Orientation

Shopping habits serve as motivational factors, as evidenced by increased shopping activity. It has consequences for understanding the preferences of consumers with diverse shopping habits (Lucia-Palacios et al., 2020b). Customer experiences have been observed in both task-oriented and leisure buying contexts (Atulkar & Kesari, 2017). The difference between task-oriented and recreational orientations significantly affects the main motivational factors. Customers who are task-oriented see shopping as a goal-directed activity, which affects how they make decisions (Janssen et al., 2021; Kumar & Kashyap, 2018).

Furthermore, task-oriented consumers often participate in cognitive activities linked to product-centric acquisitions (Büttner et al., 2014). Kaltcheva and Weitz (2006) noted that customers' motivational orientation is often influenced by necessity, leading to little or no genuine satisfaction with the shopping experience. Conversely, shoppers driven by recreational motives pursue intrinsic delight from shopping rather than only satisfying utilitarian demands. Experiential rewards, such as agreement or enthusiasm, can make this behavior happen (Meng & Xu, 2012). Voluntary participation in the buying experience results in differing levels of control that utilitarian and recreational shoppers desire to perceive throughout their shopping journey.

Furthermore, a recreational orientation profoundly shapes client purchase habits, shaping the overall characterization of shopping experiences, especially regarding entertainment (Lucia-Palacios et al., 2020a). This orientation is associated with sensory stimulation, which augments customer enjoyment and influences their subsequent shopping experiences, ultimately impacting their overall entertainment (Zamzuri et al., 2018). The correlation between customer motivational orientation and shopping behaviors has significant implications for delineating customer-centric practices (Rosenbaum et al., 2016), particularly for understanding shopping motivation and its link to purchase abandonment (Albrecht et al., 2017; Kwon et al., 2016).

How often do customers shop? Impulsive shopping behaviors are associated with frequent purchasing, reflecting changes in consumer behavior (Niemelä et al., 2017). Also, modern shopping practices in cities have been proven to affect extravagant purchases (Blake et al., 2010; Karmarkar & Bollinger, 2015). The change in customer behavior generally involves a focus on expense management, often aligned with future requirements (Kashif & Zarkada, 2015; Vrontis et al., 2011). Shopping malls have also been shown to significantly affect how people shop (El-Adly & Eid, 2016). When people plan their shopping trips well and know what they need, they have better experiences and are happier with the service. These kinds of things show how important budgeting is and how it affects people's purchasing decisions (Lucia-Palacios et al., 2016). Shopping without paying unnecessary fees, such as those incurred with credit or debit cards, reduces demands and, consequently, expenditure (Niemelä et al., 2017). Customer motivation is shaped by their predispositions and the buying surroundings (Lucia-Palacios et al., 2020b). Studies in consumer behavior reveal that individuals who have favorable shopping experiences often shape their understanding of consumer behavior through intrinsic characteristics (Elmashhara & Soares, 2019). On the other hand, consumers who have unanticipated encounters typically say that the results are surprising and that they are not always happy with them. Individuals influenced by demonstrative circumstances, lacking a pre-established goal, often exhibit excessive purchase behavior, which subsequently alters their shopping habits (Diallo et al., 2018; Haverila & Fehr, 2016).

Customers are less likely to be interested in purchasing when they see products or brands that do not look good. Shopping habits at malls have also been connected to fewer customers at regular stores (El-Adly, 2019). People in developing countries sometimes know little about malls, which are often seen as expensive places to shop (Lucia-Palacios et al., 2020a). One important way to judge how competitive businesses in shopping malls are is by how well they recruit new customers and how much they contribute. According to Merrilees and Miller (2019), stores that offer discounts in malls make customers happier and more likely to return. The evolution of mall shopping habits and their

influence on consumer behavior is significant (Atulkar & Kesari, 2017).

Conceptual Framework

Customers often overlook their influence on shopping behaviors and the resulting impact on their overall experience. They focus instead on external factors from various offerings, disregarding the tangible effects that shape their behavior. Baker and Wakefield (2012) investigated the relationship between adverse experiences and mall shopping behaviors, explicitly focusing on the effects of congestion. Childers et al. (2001) examined the impact of new interactive media on customer experiences in retail settings by evaluating motivational orientation. As a result, both internal and external influences affect how customers feel about a business (Nasution et al., 2014; Verhoef et al., 2009). Shopping can improve human mood, but only if there are many options to choose from. It is because the range of possibilities is a big part of what makes the experience enjoyable (Lucia-Palacios et al., 2018).

On the other hand, shopping at malls has been shown to enhance the experience by reducing shopping time, providing customers with more options to make better choices, and giving them greater negotiating power (Merrilees & Miller, 2019). Also, shopping in malls has made it easier for people to find good products, helping them make faster comparisons when buying (Rosenbaum et al., 2016). Shopping typically makes people more familiar with malls, more involved in the shopping process, and better able to understand the whole experience (Overby & Lee, 2006). Büttner et al. (2015) examined consumer shopping orientation, emphasizing the motivational factors that influence shopping behavior. Their findings demonstrate that these motivational factors substantially influence customers' shopping attitudes. The study also shows that non-monetary promotional aspects are crucial in influencing customer buying behaviors when combined with educational components. Chronic shopping impulses, sometimes assessed through manipulation, significantly influence shopping behavior. The study also identified task-oriented shoppers who are swayed by monetary rewards. These rewards grab customers' attention and help

businesses understand how shoppers behave, which, in turn, attracts more customers. Promotional offerings are especially appealing to customers who exhibit experienced behaviors (Ma, 2021). In a related study, Huang and Ha (2020) examined the ramifications of customer and retailer happiness, highlighting the influence of non-productive inputs on customer contentment. They discussed the hedonic approach to consumption, focusing on how it works in practice and why buyers are inclined to repeat purchases. Moreover, enhancements in the shopping environment and their impact on motivated shopping orientation were identified as contributing to favorable outcomes in overall purchasing behavior. Kaltcheva and Weitz (2006) examined the moderating effects of motivational orientation on consumer behavior, particularly arousal and pleasantness. Their findings indicate that customers derive positive arousal from their environment, as evidenced by enhanced product displays, improved visibility, clear price tags, and attractive color combinations, thereby influencing their purchasing decisions.

This study shows that it is possible to improve customer response rates. However, the complexity of the products and poor presentation have had unexpected repercussions on customer receptiveness and stress levels. Also, the effect of motivational shopping elements has been found to make buyers respond in distinct ways. Motivational orientation serves as a moderating factor in clarifying the link between customer happiness and arousal. Additionally, recreational shopping activity has been associated with the establishment of an environment that promotes arousal, integrating both pleasurable and aversive components (Chang & Cheng, 2015). In their research, van Rompay et al. (2012) emphasized the importance of shop structure, encompassing spatial and ambient design, in shaping customer experiences and their relationship with stress levels. Understanding customers' intents and the joy they derive from purchasing essentially depends on their motivational orientation. Task-oriented habits and well-organized procedures significantly affect how the business is structured. The idea of recreational input in shopping behavior and arousal helps us better understand how spatial design affects customer experiences. A well-organized

store layout builds customer trust and liking, leading to more sales and a more enjoyable shopping experience. The main goal of the store environment is to make it easy for customers to reach their goals. Customers usually choose a store depending on how well the setting helps them reach their goals (Batra & Ahtola, 1991; Voss et al., 2003). In this case, store settings might be thought of as conditions that help. Ward and Barnes (2001) stress that consumers are more likely to have a good experience in a store when they feel in control. This is because it affects how they judge whether the surroundings will help them reach their goals.

H1: There is a significant impact of customers' shopping experience on shopping behavior in shopping malls.

H2: Customer shopping motivational orientation significantly impacts shopping behavior in shopping malls.

H3: There is a significant impact of shopping frequency on shopping behavior among customers in shopping malls.

Research Methodology

Experience, frequency, and shopping motivation were examined in the context of shopping mall consumer behavior in Quetta City, Pakistan. Analyzing how independent variables affect dependent variables helps predict customer behavior and purchase patterns. The prospects of Quetta City's commercial malls are examined (Saunders, 2012). Quetta inhabitants' shopping center visits and past experiences would inform the study. Saunders & Lewis (2012) present an empirical model for several events. Tabachnick et al. (2007) examine the empirical effects of independent factors on dependent variables to determine their relationship. It suits quantitative methods (Hair et al., 2019). Customer purchases are affected by shopping experience, motivation, and frequency in quantitative cause-and-effect research. Investigators deduced. Hair et al. (2019) test theories with data. This strategy is supported and simplified by research (Saunders, 2012). This method boosts study dependability (Saunders & Lewis, 2012). Self-administered surveys are cheaper and faster than phone or in-person interviews for large groups. Researchers can obtain a larger sample at a lower cost and with fewer responses, as respondents can complete the questionnaire at their convenience.

This marketing research uses self-administered surveys.

This probe targets Quetta residents. Here, Balochi, Punjabi, Pashtun, Hazara, Bruhavi, and Afghans have different education, tastes, customs, and beliefs. Shopping habits and attitudes vary. This diverse group's features can help the study's goals by providing insights that improve research results (Saunders & Lewis, 2012).

This study used convenience sampling. This strategy allows us to collect data from free people. Convenience sampling informs. Saunders (2012). "Convenience sampling is the method of data collection that relies on members of the population who are conveniently available to participate in the study." It is best when participants are available, culturally connected, or eager (Etikan et al., 2016). Social, tribal, cultural, and sectoral barriers limit the reach of the Quetta audience. Of 600 in-person self-administered surveys, 433 (72.16%) were completed. The final analysis removed 13 incomplete questions. Self-administered questionnaires explaining the study's aims, demographics, and key components were collected in a mall's natural setting. Statistical analysis of social and behavioral studies indicates that G-power requires 135 data points, but 420 exceed this threshold (Erdfelder et al., 1996). A minimum sample size of 135 was used, with an effect size of 0.1, a type-I error rate of 0.05, and a power of 0.99.

A known-scale questionnaire was created for this study. The survey asks questions about age, gender, education, shopping habits, reasons, frequency, and behavior. Previous studies examined shopping motivation, frequency, and behavior. The complex ISCX scale was used to examine consumer experience to develop engaging, valued retail settings. This scale accurately and comprehensively measures CX qualities (Bustamante & Rubio, 2017b). Five measures measured shopping habits, frequency, and incentive, while eleven Likert scales measured consumer experience. All questionnaire segments have enough questions to ensure fairness, encourage respondent diversity, and support the study's findings. Kwon et al. (2016) examined cross-level human behavioral responses using a Likert scale. A multiple regression analysis was employed to estimate the aggregate and individual effects of

customer shopping behavior, motivational orientation, and shopping frequency on shopping behavior in retail settings. This study examined relationships among variables using multivariate statistics.

Results

The data collected for this study were analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26, which enabled both descriptive and inferential analyses to test the proposed hypotheses. Preliminary analyses, including data screening, normality tests, and reliability analyses, were conducted to ensure the accuracy and internal consistency of the measurement scales. Reliability was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha coefficients, which indicated satisfactory internal consistency for all constructs. As recommended by Nunnally and Bernstein (1994) and Hair et al. (2019), with a minimum of 0.70. After ensuring reliability, Pearson's correlation analysis was used to examine the direction and magnitude of bivariate relationships among the variables under study.

In contrast, multiple regression analysis was used to determine the relative predictive ability of customer shopping experience, motivational orientation, and shopping frequency for shopping behavior. Statistical inference was set at 0.05 and 0.01, and all diagnostic tests confirmed that the model assumptions were satisfied. The data analytic plan, conducted with a view to implementation in SPSS, provided a sound foundation for estimating presumed relations among hypothesized entities and for inferring mall shopkeeper behavior with empirical accuracy.

Reliability tests were also employed to obtain a measure of internal consistency for each construct's scales. Items for each construct appropriately gauged latent variables, as Cronbach's Alpha (α) for each scale was greater than 0.70, as Nunnally and Bernstein (1994) and Hair et al. (2019) indicate. The construct "Shopping Experience of Customers" had an alpha of 0.850, indicating satisfactory reliability and supporting the scale items' ability to capture participants' views of mall shopping experiences. The construct "Shopping Motivation Orientation" had a remarkably high alpha of 0.931, indicating extremely high internal consistency and

inferring that participants showed clear motivational patterns driving shopping activities. Likewise, "Shopping Frequency" yielded an alpha value of 0.901, indicating high scale reliability and consistent participant responses regarding mall visiting frequency. The dependent construct "Shopping Behavior" had the highest reliability,

with an alpha of 0.960, indicating near-perfect internal consistency across its seven items. This finding verifies that behavioral scales such as purchase intent, involvement, and satisfaction were estimated with great precision.

Table 1: Reliability Statistics

Variable / Construct	Cronbach's Alpha (α)	Number of Items	Reliability Level
Customers' Shopping Experience	0.850	5	Good
Shopping Motivational Orientation	0.931	7	Excellent
Shopping Frequency	0.901	5	Excellent
Shopping Behavior	0.960	7	Excellent

Moreover, the magnitude and direction of the linear relationships between the studied variables were analyzed using a correlation test. Results showed positive, statistically significant correlations for all constructs at the 0.01 level of probability, indicating that each independent variable was meaningfully related to the dependent variable. The correlation between shopping experience and shopping behavior was moderate and positive ($r = .621, p < .01$), indicating that consumers who report more intensive shopping experiences are more likely to exhibit more favorable shopping behavior, including higher purchase intentions and greater satisfaction. A stronger correlation was found between shopping behavior and shopping motivational orientation ($r =$

$.665, p < .01$), suggesting that motivational factors such as enjoyment, utility, and self-expression fundamentally influence customer behavior in mall settings. Likewise, the relationship between shopping frequency and shopping behavior was positive and significant ($r = .530, p < .01$), indicating that consumers who visit malls more often are more likely to maintain steady, active shopping behavior. Additionally, the shopping experience was significantly related to shopping motivational orientation ($r = .589, p < .01$) and shopping frequency ($r = .463, p < .01$), highlighting the interdependence among customer satisfaction, motivation, and regular shopping.

Table 2: Correlation Statistics

Variables	Shop-Behav	Shop-Exp	Shop-Mot-Orie	Shop-Frq
Shop-Behav	1			
Shop-Exp	.621**	1		
Shop-Mot-Orie	.665**	.589**	1	
Shop-Frq	.530**	.463**	.598**	1

Table 2 Regression Statistics

Predictor Variable	(B)	Std. Error	t-Value	Sig.	Confidence Interval (B)	Tolerance	VIF
Constant	0.716	1.392	0.514	0.608	[-2.030, 3.461]	-	-
Shopping Experience	0.253	0.048	5.248	0.000	[0.158, 0.348]	0.631	1.585
Shopping Motivational Orientation	0.405	0.072	5.630	0.000	[0.263, 0.547]	0.515	1.942
Shopping Frequency	0.097	0.041	2.362	0.019	[0.016, 0.178]	0.619	1.616

A multiple regression analysis was employed to estimate the aggregate and individual effects of customer shopping behavior, motivational orientation, and shopping frequency on shopping behavior in retail settings. A strong overall fit was observed, with a multiple correlation coefficient (R) of 0.732, indicating a significant linear relationship between the independent and dependent variables. A value of $R^2 = 0.535$ indicated that approximately 53.5% of the variation in shopping behavior was explained by the three independent variables combined. It was further confirmed that an adjusted R^2 of 0.528 supported the model's consistency, given the number of predictors included. Furthermore, the F-statistic ($F = 74.136$, $p < 0.001$) indicated that the regression model was statistically significant, indicating that predictors as a group influence customer shopping behavior in retail contexts.

Among the individual-level predictors, shopping motivational orientation ($\beta = 0.385$, $p < 0.001$) was the most influential in shaping shopping behavior, indicating that intrinsic and extrinsic motivations, such as hedonic pleasure, value-drivenness, and self-expression, are critically important in shaping customers' behavior. Shopping experience ($\beta = 0.324$, $p < 0.001$) also showed a significant positive relationship with shopping behavior, indicating that positive experiences in mall settings (e.g., ambiance, service, and product assortment) enrich customer participation and shopping behavior. Finally, shopping frequency ($\beta = 0.147$, $p = 0.019$) was identified as contributing a lesser but significant influence, indicating that high-frequency mall-attending customers exhibit more stable and positive shopping behaviors. Finally, collinearity statistics also reported VIF values below 2 and tolerance values above 0.5, again reaffirming no problem of multicollinearity (Hair et al., 2019). Overall, the results collectively affirm all three hypotheses (H1, H2, and H3), indicating that shopping experience, motivational orientation, and frequency contribute meaningfully to the formation of mall consumers' behavioral outcomes.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the multiple regression analysis provides robust evidence that the combined factors of shopping motivational orientation, shopping

experience, and shopping frequency are significant determinants of customer shopping behavior in retail settings. The model demonstrates strong explanatory power, accounting for over 53% of the variance in shopping behavior, and is statistically significant overall.

At the individual predictor level, the findings reveal a distinct hierarchy of influence. **The shopping motivational orientation emerges as the most potent driver, underscoring the critical roles of intrinsic and extrinsic motivations**, such as hedonic pleasure and self-expression. **Shopping experience** also exerts a substantial positive influence, confirming that elements such as ambiance, service, and product assortment are pivotal in shaping customer behavior. While still significant, **shopping frequency** contributes a comparatively lesser, yet meaningful, effect, suggesting that habitual visitors tend to exhibit more stable and positive shopping patterns.

The absence of multicollinearity further strengthens the reliability of these results. Collectively, the analysis affirms that a holistic understanding of mall consumers' behavioral outcomes requires consideration not only of their visit frequency but, more importantly, of their underlying motivations and the quality of their in-mall experiences.

Recommendations

Based on the compelling findings of this study, which confirm that motivational orientation, shopping experience, and shopping frequency collectively explain over 53% of customer shopping behavior, the following strategic actions are recommended to enhance retail performance and customer engagement; develop experiential zones, in-mall events, pop-up installations, and sensory marketing (e.g., appealing scents, music) to cater to customers seeking pleasure and entertainment. Implement and clearly communicate loyalty programs, personalized discounts, and value-for-money propositions. Curate brands and products that allow for personal identity projection and foster community through social media campaigns and brand storytelling. Maintain high standards of cleanliness, lighting, and temperature control. Incorporate comfortable seating and relaxing common areas. Train staff in advanced customer

service, product knowledge, and problem-solving to ensure positive interactions. Use data analytics to ensure a well-curated, diverse product mix that meets local demand and avoids out-of-stock situations.

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